

COMPARATIVE ISOLATION, IDENTIFICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BACTERIA IN FOOD AND WATER FROM SELECTED CANTEENS IN AKURE AND ILARA-MOKIN, ONDO STATE, NIGERIA.

*¹Momoh, A. O., ¹Fadare, O. S., ²Asowata-Ayodele, A. M., ³Ogonnoh, O. B., ¹Ayodele, A. M. and ¹Richard-Egbegiri, F. O.

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Basic and Applied Sciences, Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Ondo State, Nigeria.

²Department of Biosciences and Biotechnology, Plant Biology and Biotechnology Unit, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

³Department of Microbiology, School of Life Sciences, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Article Info

Article Received: 03 October 2025,
Article Revised: 25 October 2025,
Published on: 01 November 2025.

*Corresponding author:
Momoh, A. O.

Department of Biological Sciences,
Faculty of Basic and Applied Sciences,
Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Ondo
State, Nigeria.
abdulmomoh@elizadeuniversity.edu.ng

How to cite this Article:

*¹Momoh, A. O., ¹Fadare, O. S.,
²Asowata-Ayodele, A. M., ³Ogonnoh, O.
B., ¹Ayodele, A. M. and ¹Richard-
Egbegiri, F. O. COMPARATIVE
ISOLATION, IDENTIFICATION AND
CHARACTERIZATION OF BACTERIA
IN FOOD AND WATER FROM
SELECTED CANTEENS IN AKURE AND
ILARA-MOKIN, ONDO STATE,
NIGERIA. World Journal of
Pharmaceutical and Healthcare
Research, 2(11), 7-16.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17511122>

This work is licensed under Creative
Commons Attribution 4.0
International license.

ABSTRACT

Background: There is a rise in infection as a result of food from canteens and restaurants in Ondo State. This research aims to verify whether cooked ready-to-eat foods and water served at major canteens are the major vehicle of transmission of microorganisms. Also, to verify if the water served during the meal to customers meet the World Health Standard for drinking water rather than spread pathogenic microorganisms to customers. **Methods:** Prepared food and water served to customers were collected from two canteens each from Akure Ilara-Mokin respectively. They were analyzed using standard microbiological methods. The bacterial loads, type, antibiotic sensitivity and sequencing of the most common isolate from food and water was done for each canteen. **Results:** The predominant bacteria genera in food from Akure was *Staphylococcus*, while the ones from Ilara-Mokin was *Klebsiella*. The genera *Klebsiella*, *Escherichia* and *Citrobacter* were common to water from both towns. The highest bacterial load from food sample was 3.0×10^4 cfu/gm, while that of water was 2.0×10^3 cfu/ml. The 16S RNA sequencing and blast result confirmed the identity of isolate from Akure food sample to be *Mammaliococcus sciuri* (accession number of KM243920.1) while from water sample was confirmed to be *Escherichia coli* with accession number CP099005.1. The one from Ilara-Mokin food was *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (accession number CP028391.2) while from the water sample was *Escherichia coli* with accession number of CP104618.1. All the three bottle water samples from the Elizade University school canteen were free of bacterial contamination and complied with World Health Organization (WHO) standard for drinking water. **Conclusion:** The results obtained have shown that the food and water samples from these canteens are far from the microbiological standard expected of them and needs improvement on the food safety level to prevent food borne infection.

KEYWORDS: Cooked-Food, Served-water, Bacteria, WHO-Standard.

BACKGROUND

Several definitions exist for microbiological quality of food and water ready to be consumed by customers or people. Generally, it indicates the number of microbial contaminants it has, and a high level of contamination indicates low quality of such food. The storage and handling of food and water are more likely involved in transmission of diseases.^[1] Bacterial count in prepared food and water is a key factor in assessing the quality and safety of food. It also reveals the level of hygiene adopted by food handlers in the course of preparation of such foods. Food and water in

particular have been described as vehicle for the transmission of microbial disease among which are those caused by coliforms.^[2]

Ready-to-eat foods can be described as foods and beverages that can be bought directly from street vendors, hawkers or restaurants and are consumed at the point of sale or at later time without further processing. It could be raw or cooked, hot or chilled and consumed without further treatment.^[3] Examples of such ready-to-eat foods among others include rice, eba, salad, beans, moi-moi and porridge. While it is

expected that the nutritional needs of the consumers should be met via the consumption of street foods, it is also necessary to ensure their safety from contaminants (microorganisms). Safe food is a basic human right despite the fact that many foods are frequently contaminated with naturally occurring pathogenic microorganisms which cannot be detected organoleptically (seen, smelled or tasted) but can cause serious diseases including death especially if the way they are conserved during exposition for sale provides the condition for those microorganisms to grow and reach considerable levels of contamination.^[4] There are many reasons why people eat away from home; these include among others absence from home while traveling, studying, at work or need for a change in terms of food type or location and as such, many people resort to buying street-vended food. Most of these foods are often poorly processed, especially in poor African countries where regulatory agencies are not up and doing.^[5]

This situation however, has resulted to the transfer of food sanitary measures and proper food handling from individuals/families to the food vendors who rarely enforce such practices.^[6] An estimated 2.5 billion people patronize food-vendors worldwide daily.^[7]

The majority of people and students on campus don't prepare food themselves but buy and take it along with them to the campus and this has led to an increase in demand for food which gives opportunity to cafeterias and canteens to serve as the major vending sites were both staff and students purchase food daily. In most cases these foods are not adequately processed, and protection from flies and usually refrigeration may be unavailable. This unhygienic condition under which food vendors operate couple with their lack of basic hygienic safety has led to this present study.

Food, which is known majorly as the fundamental unit of living cells' source of energy, has been studied to have several types of intrinsic and extrinsic factors. These factors include hydrogen ion concentration (pH), water activity (a_w), redox potential (eh), different types of nutrients, antimicrobial substances, temperature, and environmental conditions for storage that regulate the growth of pathogenic microorganisms responsible for food spoilage, poisoning, and toxicities, as well as foodborne illness.^[8] Hence, the importance of this research in Akure and Ilara-Mokin towns cannot be overemphasized. This research aims to isolate, identify and characterize bacteria in food and water from selected canteens in Akure and Ilara-Mokin, Ondo State, Nigeria.

METHODS

Type of study

This is a food safety study that involves cross-sectional evaluation of foods that are ready-to-eat from selected canteens. The duration of this study was for a period of three (3) months. The site for sample collection was road block in Akure; Ilara-Mokin central Market canteen and the

Elizade University student canteens. All autoclaving was done at 121 °C for 15 minutes.^[9]

Collection of samples

A total of eight samples (two food and two water samples from two canteens a and b from Akure town and Ilara-Mikon respectively) were collected. These food samples include: jollof rice from Akure market area and the water (pure water) they served the customers to drink. The samples were placed aseptically in sterile polythene bags and transported to the laboratory within thirty minutes of collection.^[10]

The media used in this research are nutrient agar (Fluka), maconkey agar (Scharlau), eosine methylene blue agar (Scharlau), Salmonella-Shigella agar (Oxoid), and Thiosulphate citrate bile-salt agar (oxoid).^[10]

Sample analysis

The pour plate technique was used for plating out the appropriate dilutions of the sample. (10^{-2} and 10^{-3}). One millilitre of each dilution 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} were pipette and transferred into separate triplicate well labelled sterile Petri dishes. Molten agar cooled to 45 °C was poured over with the sample in each plate. Immediately, the sample and the molten agar were thoroughly and uniformly mixed by a gentle alternate rotation of the plates on the work bench. The solidified agar plates were inverted and incubated at 35 °C for 24 hours for the Nutrient agar plate for total viable counts, 37 °C for 24-48 hours for McConkey agar plates for coliform/Enterobacteriaceae counts and the same process for salmonella-shigella and eosin-methylene blue agar. The cultured plates were examined after incubation and colonies per plates were counted and recorded for estimation of colony forming unit per gram (cfu/g) of the original sample.^[11]

Bacteria Colony Count

The visible colonies were counted in the nutrient agar plate with a colony counter and recorded based on their dilution factor:

$$\text{Number of organisms} = \frac{\text{Number of colonies}}{0.1} \times \frac{\text{Dilution factor}}{1}$$

Isolation After counting the colonies on the agar plates, the observed growths were sub cultured to obtain pure isolates on newly prepared agar plates. This was achieved by inoculating the individual colonies in a nutrient agar plate and incubated between 35-37°C for 24 hours. The isolates were subsequently stored at 4°C in the refrigerator for identification process.^[12]

Identification of isolates

Bacterial isolates were characterized to generic level and where possible to the species level on the basis of their cultural features (i.e. colour, shape, edge, elevation, etc), morphological features (features such as motility, gram-reaction, cell arrangement, and shape) and biochemical features. The results obtained were then compared with

standard references for proper identification of the isolates. Bergey's manual was used for bacteria identification.^[12]

DNA Extraction

DNA extraction from all the bacteria isolates for PCR assays was done using the ZymoBIOMICS™ DNA Miniprep kit according to the manufacturer guide.^[13]

Sequencing of Bacteria Isolates

After the genomic DNA was extracted from the cultures received using the Quick-DNA™ Fungal/Bacterial Miniprep kit (Zymo research catalogue number D6005. The 16S target region was amplified using OneTaq Quick-load 2X Master Mix 9NEB, Catalogue number M0486) with primers presented on table 1. The PCR products were run on a gel and cleaned up enzymatically using the EXOSAP method. The extracted fragments were sequenced in the forward and reverse direction (Nimagen, Brilliant Dye™ Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit V3.1, BRD3-100/1000) and purified (Zymo Research, ZR-96 DNA Sequencing Clean-up Kit™, Catalogue number D4050). The purified fragments were analyzed on the ABI 3500XL Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, ThermoFisher Scientific) for each reaction for every sample, as listed in Section 1. BioEdit Sequence Alignment Editor version 7.2.5 was used to analyze the ab1 files generated by the ABI 3500XL Genetic Analyzer and results were obtained by a BLAST search (NCBI).

Susceptibility testing

Antibiotic susceptibility of the isolates was determined by disc diffusion assay following CLSI guidelines.^[14] The bacteria were tested for susceptibility against amoxycillin, cephalosporin, gentamicin, amikacin, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, ciprofloxacin, netilmicin and piperacillin. They are commercial antibiotics prepared and marketed by Optu disc, United States of America. All the assay was done in triplicate and the result subjected to statistical analysis.

Table 1: 16S rRNA primers sequences.

Name of Primer	Target	Sequence (5' to 3')
16S-27F	16S rDNA sequence	AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG
16S-1492R	16S rDNA sequence	CGGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT

RESULTS

Table 2a shows the bacterial load and types of bacteria isolated from each of the food sample from the two canteens from Akure and their water sample analyzed for enteric bacteria, while table 2b is the result from Ilara-Mokin. From Akure, the predominant bacteria were in the food was *Staphylococcus aureus*, while the ones from the water sample were *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli* and *Citrobacter freundii*. The food sample with the highest bacterial load was food sample b 3 with a load of 3.0×10^4 cfu/gm. From this sample, three (3) different bacteria were identified and they are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Escherichia coli*. Also,

the water samples gotten from the canteens were not sterile. Three of the six water samples obtained from the two canteens had a bacterial load of 2.0×10^3 cfu/ml and had bacteria such as *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Enterobacter aerogenes*.

From Ilara town, the predominant bacteria that were isolated from the food samples from the first canteen (from town) was the genera *Klebsiella*. The bacteria were present in the three samples collected from the canteen for the consecutive three days of sample collection. On the other hand, the bacteria from the water sample were *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from the same canteen in Ilara town.

The food sample with the highest bacterial load was food sample A 1 with a load of 2.3×10^4 cfu/gm. From this sample, three (3) different bacteria were identified and they are *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Also, the water samples gotten from the canteens were equally high in bacterial load with the highest having 2.0×10^3 cfu/ml and bacteria such as *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Escherichia coli*. Generally, all the three water samples from the Elizade University school canteen (Cafeteria 1) were free of bacterial contamination. Of the six water samples obtained from the two canteens the highest bacterial load of 2.0×10^3 cfu/ml and had bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* and *Enterobacter aerogenes*.

Tables 3a and 3b shows the number of water samples that had no form of coliform in it and was tagged negative when subjected to incubation at 44.5°C for 24 hours. Only two of the water samples tested negative to this test as there was no growth at this temperature. On the other hand, table 4 defined the level of compliance of the water samples to WHO approved standard for drinking water. There is none of the water samples from Akure evaluated met the WHO standard based on the number of colonies forming unit obtained for each sample as they were all had high microbial loads. Table 5 shows the results of the identification procedure and the number of the bacteria as well as the names of the bacteria isolated. A total of eight bacteria were identified from both the food samples and water samples from the canteens. The morphological characteristics, gram's staining reactions, spore test, motility and biochemical characteristics such as catalase, oxidase and hydrogen sulfide tests as well as the sugar fermentation tests gave rise to eight different isolates from the two canteens. A total of six isolates were gotten from the food samples and they are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Citrobacter freundii* while two that includes *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Proteus vulgaris* were isolated from the water samples in addition to the already isolated ones from the food samples, except, *Staphylococcus*.

Table 2a: Bacterial load and types isolated from Akure food and water samples.

S/N	Sample Identity	Bacterial Load (Cfu/ml/Gm)	Bacterial Type
1	Food A 1	1.0×10 ⁴	<i>Staphylococcus aureus, Enterobacter aerogenes, Proteus vulgaris</i>
2	Food A 2	2.0×10 ⁴	<i>Escherichia coli, Enterobacter aerogenes, Staphylococcus aureus</i>
3	Food A 3	1.1×10 ⁴	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes, Escherichia coli, Bacillus subtilis</i>
4	Food B 1	1.0×10 ⁴	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes, Staphylococcus aureus</i>
5	Food B 2	1.1×10 ⁴	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae, Escherichia coli, Citrobacter freundii, Staphylococcus aureus</i>
6	Food B 3	3.0×10 ⁴	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes, Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus aureus</i>
7	Water A 1	2.0×10 ³	<i>Escherichia coli, Proteus vulgaris</i>
8	Water A 2	1.1×10 ³	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae, Escherichia coli, Citrobacter freundii</i>
9	Water A 3	1.3×10 ³	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Proteus vulgaris</i>
10	Water B 1	1.0×10 ³	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>
11	Water B 2	2.0×10 ³	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes, Escherichia coli</i>
12	Water B 3	2.0×10 ³	<i>Proteus vulgaris, Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>

Table 2b: Bacterial load and types of bacteria isolated from Ilara-Mokin food and water samples

S/N	Sample identity	Bacterial load (cfu/ml/gm)	Bacterial type
1	Food A 1	2.3×10 ⁴	<i>Escherichia coli, Proteus vulgaris, Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
2	Food A 2	1.4×10 ⁴	<i>Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Enterobacter aerogenes</i>
3	Food A 3	2.0×10 ⁴	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes, Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
4	Food B 1	1.2×10 ⁴	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes, Staphylococcus aureus</i>
5	Food B 2	1.0×10 ⁴	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae, Escherichia coli</i>
6	Food B 3	1.1×10 ⁴	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae, Enterobacter aerogenes</i>
7	Water A 1	2.0×10 ³	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes, Escherichia coli</i>
8	Water A 2	1.1×10 ³	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae, Escherichia coli</i>
9	Water A 3	1.3×10 ³	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes, Escherichia coli</i>
10	Water B 1	1.0×10 ¹	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>
11	Water B 2	0.0×10 ¹	None
12	Water B 3	0.0×10 ¹	None

Table 3a: Faecal coliform test for Akure water samples at 44.5°c.

S/N	Sample Identity	Production Of Acid	Production Of Gas	Remarks
1	Water A 1	Yes	Yes	Positive
2	Water A 2	Yes	Yes	Positive
3	Water A 3	No	No	Negative
4	Water B 1	No	No	Negative
5	Water B 2	Yes	Yes	Positive
6	Water B 3	Yes	Yes	Positive

Table 3b: Faecal Coliform test for water samples at 44.5° c.

S/N	Sample identity	Production of Acid	Production of Gas	Remarks
1	Water A 1	Yes	Yes	Positive
2	Water A 2	Yes	Yes	Positive
3	Water A 3	Yes	Yes	Positive
4	Water B 1	No	No	Negative
5	Water B 2	No	No	Negative
6	Water B 3	No	No	Negative

Table 4a: compliance of Akure drinking water sample with WHO standard of drinkable water.

S/N	Sample Identity	Bacterial Load (Cfu/MI)	Bacterial Counts	Compliance With Who Standard
1	Water A 1	2.0×10 ³	2000	No
2	Water A 2	1.1×10 ³	1100	No
3	Water A 3	1.3×10 ³	1300	No
4	Water B 1	1.0×10 ³	1000	No
5	Water B 2	2.0×10 ³	2000	No
6	Water B 3	2.0×10 ³	2000	No

Table 4b: Compliance of Ilara-Mokin water sample with WHO standard of drinkable water

S/N	Sample identity	Bacterial load (cfu/ml)	Bacterial Counts	Compliance with WHO standard
1	Water A 1	2.0×10 ³	2000	No
2	Water A 2	1.1×10 ³	1100	No
3	Water A 3	1.3×10 ³	1300	No
4	Water B 1	1.0×10 ¹	1	Yes
5	Water B 2	0.0×10 ¹	0	Yes
6	Water B 3	0.0×10 ¹	0	Yes

Table 5: biochemical characteristics of bacterial isolates.

Isolate No	Cat	Oxi	Ind	H ₂ s	Nit Red	Ure	Lact	Fruc	Malt	Gala	Glu	Arab	Raf	Man	Mr	Vp	Identified Organism
1	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Enterobacter Aerogenes</i>
2	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	<i>Escherichia Coli</i>
3	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Klebsiella Pneumoniae</i>
4	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Proteus Vulgaris</i>
5	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Bacillus Subtilis</i>
6	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Citrobacter Freundii</i>
7	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus Aureus</i>
8	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	<i>Pseudomonas Aeruginosa</i>

Results of sequencing of bacteria isolates

A total four bacteria (the most common bacteria from food and water from Akure and most common from food and water from Ilara-Mokin) were sequenced or subjected to the 16s rRNA sequencing and their identity presented on Tables 5a and b respectively. The 16s rRNA sequencing and blast result from Akure food and water confirmed the identity of the most frequent isolate from food sample to be *Mammaliicoccus sciuri* (having a genbank accession number of KM243920.1) while the isolate from the water sample was confirmed to be *Escherichia coli* with a GenBank accession number of CP099005.1. This result is presented in table 5a. The result confirmed the identity of isolate from Ilara-Mokin food sample to be *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (having a GenBank Accession number of CP028391.2) while the isolate from water sample was confirmed to be *Escherichia coli* with a GenBank Accession number of CP104618.1. This result is presented in table 5b.

Figure 1a shows the susceptibility of the isolates from Akure food and water samples to different antibiotics they were subjected to. Most of the isolates were susceptible to ciprofloxacin, except the two-gram positive bacteria that were not too susceptible to it. *Bacillus cereus* was most susceptible too gentamycin, the highest diameter of zone of inhibition of 18.67±1.15mm was obtained for *E. coli*. Figure 1b on the other hand is the susceptibility profile of isolates from Ilara-Mokin food and water samples. Comparatively, isolates from Ilara-Mokin were less susceptible to the antibiotics than isolates from Akure.

Table 6a: BLAST (Basic local alignment search tool) result.

Isolates	Most common isolate from food sample	Most common isolate from water sample
Percentage Id	99.12%	99.73%
Predicted Organism	<i>Mammaliicoccus Sciuri</i>	<i>Escherichia Coli</i>
Genbank Accession	Km243920.1	Cp099005.1

Table 6b: BLAST (Basic local alignment search tool) result.

Isolates	Most common isolate from food sample	Most common isolate from water Sample
Percentage ID	99.73%	99.89%
Predicted Organism	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
GenBank Accession	CP028391.2	CP104618.1

Figure 1a: Antibiotic susceptibility profile of isolates from Akure food and water samples.

Figure 1b: Antibiotic susceptibility profile of isolates from Ilara-Mokin food and water samples.

4	SSA (WC)	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	99.89%	CP104618.1
---	----------	-------------------------	--------	------------

TTTTGATCATGGCTCAGATTGAACGCTGGCGGCAGGCCTAACACATGCAAGTGAACGGTAACAGGAAGCAGCTTGCTGCTTCGCTGAC
GAGTGGCGGACGGGTGAGTAATGTCTGGGAACTGCCTGATGGAGGGGGATAACTACTGGAAACGGTAGCTAATACCGCATAACGTCGC
AAGACCAAAGAGGGGGACCTTCGGGCCTCTTGCCATCGGATGTGCCAGATGGGATTAGCTAGTAGGTGGGGTAACGGCTCACCTAGGC
GACGATCCCTAGCTGGTCTGAGAGGATGACCAGCCACACTGGAAGTGAACAGCGGTCCAGACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTGGGGAATA
TTGCACAATGGGCGCAAGCCTGATGCAGCCATGCCGCGTGTATGAAGAAGGCCTTCGGGTTGTAAAGTACTTTCAGCGGGGAGGAAGG
GAGTAAAGTTAATACCTTTGCTCATTGACGTTACCCGCGAGAAGAAGCACCAGGCTAACTCCGTGCCAGCAGCCGCGTAATACGGAGGGT
GCAAGCGTTAATCGGAATTACTGGGCGTAAAGCGCACGCAGGCGGTTTGTAAAGTCAAGTGTGAAATCCCCGGGCTCAACCTGGGAAGT
GCATCTGATACTGGCAAGCTTGAGTCTCGTAGAGGGGGGTAGAATTCCAGGTGTAGCGGTGAAATGCGTAGAGATCTGGAGGAATACCG
GTGGCGAAGGCGGCCCCCTGGACGAAGACTGACGCTCAGGTGCGAAAGCGTGGGGAGCAAACAGGATTAGATACCTGGTAGTCCACGC
CGTAAACGATGTCGACTTGGAGGTTGTGCCCTTGAGCGGTGGCTTCCGGAGCTAACGCGTTAAGTCGACCCGCCTGGGGAGTACGCGCC

DISCUSSION

The outbreaks of food-borne diseases such as cholera, typhoid, dysentery, etc. are on the increase in Nigeria and Africa at large. Sometimes, food may also become poisonous due to the ingestion of some toxic chemicals produced by microorganisms or may be contaminated by pathogenic microbes due to the mistreatment of food^[15], improper way of food processing and preparation, mixing of different types of flavoring agents without knowing its ingredients and reactions, intake of reheating food, unhealthy cooking and consumption policy.^[16]

These factors are seen in this research in which both the food and water samples contain an array of bacteria. Consumption of these already contaminated food or foods infested by insects, use of an excessive number of preservatives, or improper way of storage may be the main causes of sickness; hospitalizations eventually leading to death and can be referred to as foodborne diseases.^[17]

The bacterial loads of the prepared foods from the canteens showed the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* as the predominant bacteria which was present in all the food samples from both Akure and Ilara canteens respectively. Similar researches done in several countries had similar results in which *staphylococcus aureus* was isolated and identified according to.^{[18]&[19]} The predominant bacteria from the water samples were *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli* and *Citrobacter freundii*. These results were similar to the results obtained by.^{[20]&[21]} The food sample with the highest bacterial load was food sample b 3 with a load of 3.0×10^4 cfu/gm and this probably due to the unhygienic nature of where the canteen was located, which is very close to an open-air market.

The three (3) different bacteria that were identified from this food sample from Ilara a pathogenic, which are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Escherichia coli*. These bacteria have been implicated in food intoxication and food poisoning as well as the later two in drinking water samples as documented by.^[22] Also, the water samples gotten from the canteens could be said not to be sterile. Ideally, according to^[23] drinking water should be sterile or at least be void of coliform. While all the water samples from Akure canteens did not meet these criteria, only three of the six water samples obtained from

Ilara (Elizade University cafeteria) met the criteria. This should be of great concern because according to,^[24] they can help disseminate an epidemic disease such as cholera within few days and this should call for alarm.

The presence of bacteria such as *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Enterobacter aerogenes* according to,^[25] in drinking water is dangerous for the populace depending on such water for their survival. Weather in packaged containers (pure water or bottled water), most of these bacteria can survive in water for days due to the presence of some physicochemical in the water. The presence of coliform in the water sample was confirmed by subjecting them to incubation at 44.5°C for 24hours further confirming the risk of the consumers especially anyone that may be immune-compromised^[26] and the source of the water to be polluted with faecal contaminants.

Only two of the water samples from Akure tested negative to this test as there was no growth of *Escherichia coli* at this temperature and none of the water samples complied to WHO approved standard for drinking water according to.^[27] Therefore, none of the water sample evaluated from Akure town met the WHO standard based on the number of colonies forming unit obtained for each sample as they were all having high bacterial loads. The result is an indication of the poor quality of water supplied to the customers eating in these canteens.

The total number of bacteria identified from both the food samples and water samples from the canteens in Akure and Ilara shows the level microbial pollution on the foods and water at these canteens, therefore, they are serving as vehicles for the spread of infectious diseases caused by the microorganisms. According to,^[28] the canteens are public places that are very important in public health as they act as fast vehicles of microbial dissemination.

In conclusion, the fact that *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common corroborate previous research on foodborne infection in which *S. aureus* was most implicated according to.^[29] These bacteria are known world-wide for majority of poisoning cases in different countries where there has been an outbreak of food borne infections. Bacteria such as *Enterobacter aerogenes*,

Proteus vulgaris, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Citrobacter freundii* are more common in water that its source is polluted with faecal discharge or is situated near soak-away,^[30] while *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is common in putrefactive environment, they could be leached into the ground water as well.

The two isolates (one isolate from water sample and one isolate from the food sample) from each town were subjected to the 16S rRNA sequencing and their identity confirmed the identity of isolates using colonial and biochemical characteristics. However, while the former method identified the one from the food sample as *S. aureus*, the sequencing identified it as *Mammaliococcus sciuri* (having a GenBank accession number of KM243920.1) while the isolate from water sample was confirmed to be *Escherichia coli* with a genbank accession number of CP099005.1.

The two isolates are said to be pathogenic opportunistic bacteria of food and water. although mostly exhibiting a commensal lifestyle on its animal hosts, *M. sciuri* has been occasionally identified as an opportunistic pathogen associated with mastitis, dermatitis, and exudative epidermitis.^[31] *Mammaliococcus sciuri*,

previously *Staphylococcus sciuri*, is a gram-positive, oxidase-positive, coagulase-negative member of the bacterial genus mammaliococcus consisting of clustered cocci.^[32] With the identities of these bacteria confirmed by sequencing, it is clear that most of the infections which have been traced to *Staphylococcus aureus* were actually caused *Mammaliococcus sciuri* and is from the canteens' foods. Hence, the aim of this research has been achieved.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained have shown that the food and water samples from these canteens are far from the standard microbiological level expected of them. Therefore, there is need for improvement of the quality of personal hygiene, environmental hygiene and purification of water used for serving foods prepared for customers.

Food handlers should be educated thoroughly on the importance of food, food poisoning and food intoxication to the society. sources of water, both for drinking and cooking should be checked constantly and treated appropriately. Results like this from research should be presented to them so that they know and assess their performance of food hygiene level.

Plate 1: Photograph of sugar fermentation test.

Plate 2: Photomicrograph of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* on TCBS from food sample.

Plate 3: Photomicrograph of *Enterobacter aerogenes* from water samples.

ABBREVIATIONS

SD: Standard deviation; CLSI: Clinical and laboratory standard institute; SPSS: Statistical Package for Social Science; ANOVA: Analysis of variance; WHO: World Health Organization.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

The study was approved by the Local Ethical Committee of Elizade University. Written consent was obtained from every health center prior to the procedures. This study has been carried out in accordance with the code of Ethics of the Ondo State Hospitals' Management Board, Nigeria.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION: Not applicable.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are not publicly available but are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

FUNDING

The project was funded by all the authors who came together to contribute money and material to run the research.

Financial disclosure: None

Authors and Affiliations

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Basic and Applied Sciences, Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Ondo State, Nigeria.

²Department of Biosciences and Biotechnology, Plant Biology and Biotechnology Unit, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

³Department of Microbiology, School of Life Sciences, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author's Email: - abdul.momoh@elizadeuniversity.edu.ng

Phone number: [+2348036530924](tel:+2348036530924)

CONTRIBUTIONS

MAO, FOS, OSA and OOB conceived and designed research. MAO, AAM and RFO conducted experiments. MAO, AAM, FOS and RFO analyzed data. MAO, FOS, AAM and OOB wrote the manuscript. All authors proofread the manuscript.

Corresponding author

Correspondence to Momoh, A.O.

REFERENCES

1. Banwo, K. O.-D. Functional importance of bioactive compounds of foods with Potential Health Benefits: A review on recent trends. *Food Bioscience*, 2021:43: 101320.
2. Monteiro, A. R., Silver, A. S., & Silva, D. F. Study on the influence of physicochemical parameters on the water quality index in the Maranhao 2022: 8(2), 20-36.
3. Alvarez-Suarez, J. M., Gasparrini, M., Forbes-Hernandez, T. Y., Mazzoni, L., & Giampieri, F. Food and Food Infections. *Foods*, 2019 30(3), 421-443.
4. WHO. Drinking Water Quality and Public Foods. *World Health Organization*, 2023; 31.
5. WHO. Guidelines on food quality. *World Health Organization*. (2021): Factsheet 8
6. Adesulu-Dahunsi, A. T. Synergistic Microbial Interactions between lactic acid bacteria and yeast in Nigerian Indigenous fermented foods. *Food Control*, 2020 110(3), 119-136.
7. Nyarangaro, T. E., Loureiro, V., & Querol, A. The prevalence and control of spoilage yeasts in foods and beverages. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 2019 10(11), 356-365.
8. Juliana, G. J., Machado, V., Pardo, L., Cuello, D., Giudice, G., Luna, P., et al. Staphylococcus aureus recovered from food and cases of food borne diseases. *Rev Institute of Medicine in Tropics*, 2020: 62(10), 1-10.
9. Prescott, L. M., Harley, J. P., Klein, D. A., & Adidas, J. *General Microbiology*. New York: McGrawhill. 2021 Pp 980.

10. Cheesbrough, M. *Distric Laboratory Practice in Tropical Countries*. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press. 2014 Pp362.
11. Ashaolu, T. J. Immune boosting functional foods and their mechanisms: A critical evaluation of probiotics and prebiotics. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 2020: 130, 110625.
12. Baker, F. J. *Medical Laboratory Science*. United Kingdom: Chris Publisher, 2021:. Pp 368.
13. Ojo, G. J., Onile, O. S., Momoh, A. O., Oyeyemi, B. F., Omoboyede, V., Fadahunsi, A. I., & Onile, T. Evaluation of heavy metal resistant genes in bacteria isolated from soil and water samples from Ilesha gold mines, Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology*, 2023: 21(4), 172-188.
14. Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI). Antibiotic measurement standard. *Clinical and Laboratory Standard 2023*, Pp185.
15. Triches, R. M. Food and Infection Sources. *Food and Infection*, 2020: 44(3), 881-894.
16. Juliana, G. J., Machado, V., Pardo, L., Cuello, D., Giudice, G., Luna, P., et al. Staphylococcus aureus recovered from food and cases of food borne diseases. *Rev Institute of Medicine in Tropics*, 2023 64 (3), 12-26.
17. Machado, V. P. Presence of genes encoding Enterotoxins in Staphylococcus aureus recovered from food. *Food Borne Diseases*, 2020, 62(4), 1-10.
18. Ibrahim, T. N., Oladayo, F. O., Galadima, M., Nuhu, I. T., Olufemi, O. F., & Galadima, M.. Prevalence of Staphylococcus aureus and Escherichia coli in Sun-cured meat. *International Journal Science and Clinical Research*, 2021: 1(1), 46-51.
19. Lee, A., De-Lencastre, H., Garau, J., Kluytmans, J., Malhotra-Kumar, S., & Peschel, A. Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus aureus from food sample. *Natural Review of Diseases*, 2018; 4, 1-23.
20. Freu, G., Tomaz, I. T., Filho, A., Heinemann, M., & Dos-Santos, M. V. Antimicrobial resistance and molecular characterization of Staphylococcus aureus recovered from cows with clinical mastitis in dairy herds. *Antibiotics*, 2022 11, 1-11.
21. WHO. Reviewd Guidelines on food quality. *World Health Organization*, 2021, 36.
22. Nwidi, L. L., Oveh, B., Okoriye, T., & Vaikosen, N. Assessment Of The Water Quality And Prevalence Of Water Borne Diseases In Amassoma, Niger Delta, Nigeria. *African Journal of Microbiology*, 2018 18(3), 16-31
23. WHO. Guidelines on foods, Water and environment. *World Health Organization*, 2021: 44.
24. Nguendo-Tongsi, H.. Microbiological Evaluation of Drinking Water In A Sub-Saharan Urban Community (Yaounde). *American Journal of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*, 2021 1(3), 68-81.
25. Monteiro, A. R., Silver, A. S., & Silva, D. F. Study on the influence of physicochemical parameters on the water quality index in the Maranhao 2022:. 8(2), 20-36.
26. Longhi, C., Maurizi, L., Conte, A. L., Marazzato, M., Comanducci, A., Nicoletti, M., et al. Extraintestinal Pathogenic Escherichia Coli: Beta-Lactam Antibiotic And Heavy Metal Resistance. *Antibiotics*, 2022, 11(3), 45-62.
27. WHO. Updated Drinking Water Quality and Public Foods. *World Health Organization 2023*;119.
28. Lee, A., De-Lencastre, H., Garau, J., Kluytmans, J., Malhotra-Kumar, S., & Peschel, A. Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus aureus from food sample. *Natural Review of Diseases*, 2018: 4, 1-23.
29. 29-Dak, M. Bod – Biochemical Oxygen Demand (Principle, Procedure & Application). *Biokimicroki*, 2021: 55(4), 30-38.
30. Meléndez-Martínez, A. J., Mandić, A. I., Bantis, F., Böhm, V., Borge, G. I. A., Brnčić, M., et al. A comprehensive review on carotenoids in foods and feeds: Status quo, applications, patents, and research needs. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 2022; 62(8), 1999-2049.
31. Oyenih, A. B., Belay, Z. A., Mditshwa, A., & Caleb, O. J. “An apple a day keeps the doctor away”: The potentials of apple bioactive constituents for chronic disease prevention. *Journal of Food Science*. 2022; 19 (2) 116-129.
32. Phiri, S., Schoustra, S. E., van den Heuvel, J., Smid, E. J., Shindano, J., & Linnemann, A. R. How processing methods affect the microbial community composition in a cereal-based fermented beverage. *LWT*, 2020; 128, 109451.